

THE EFFECT OF CREATIVITY, BUSINESS LOCATION AND HALAL LABELS ON THE INCOME OF SALE BANANA BUSINESS ACTORS IN EAST ACEH

Rahmatillah¹, Agustinawati², M. Subhan³

Universitas Malikussaleh, Lhokseumawe

Faculty of Economics and Business, Entrepreneurship Study Program, Lhokseumawe

E-mail: rahmatillah.210450038@mhs.unimal.ac.id¹, agustinawati@unimal.ac.id², msubhan@unimal.ac.id³

Correspondence Author: agustinawati@unimal.ac.id

Received : 10 March 2026

Accepted : 01 April 2026

Revised : 15 March 2026

Published : 18 April 2026

Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of creativity, business location, and halal labeling on the income of banana sales business actors in East Aceh. The research sample amounted to 35 respondents of banana sale business actors. The data were analyzed using multiple linear regression and the results showed that the creativity variable (X1) had a positive and significant effect, business location (X2) and halal label (X3) had no significant effect on the income of banana sale business actors in East Aceh. So this research contributes to efforts to increase the income of banana sales business actors through strengthening creativity optimally. The implication of this research is that the higher the creativity of business actors in products, services, and innovation, the greater the potential to increase banana sales business income in East Aceh.

Keywords: *Creativity, Business Location, Halal Label, Income*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship plays an important role in supporting a country's economy because it can create jobs and improve the welfare of the community. Aceh is one of the provinces with great economic potential, supported by its rich natural resources and creative human resources (Maulana, 2023). The economic sector in Aceh is very diverse, including the culinary, agricultural, service, and trade industries. The culinary sector is one of the sectors that continues to grow because food products are always needed by the community (Subhan, 2021) and are a tourist attraction for visitors who want to enjoy local specialties (Agustinawati, 2024). Each region has its own specialty products, such as Gayo coffee from Central Aceh, nutmeg candy from South Aceh, melinjo from Pidie, chips from Bireuen, and banana chips from East Aceh (Arlena, 2023). One of the regions that has shown significant development in the culinary sector is East Aceh Regency.

East Aceh is known for its prominence in the development of traditional cuisine, particularly banana sale, which has become an icon of the region and a major source of income for the community (Arida, 2019). The Pante Bidari subdistrict, especially Lhoknibong Village, is known as the largest center of pisang sale production in East Aceh and has earned the nickname "Banana Sale City" (Asrarul Aini, 2018). This product is made from high-quality local bananas using traditional processes to preserve its authentic flavor. In addition to providing economic opportunities, the banana sale business also reflects the creativity of the community in combining local wisdom with innovation to increase the competitiveness of the product in a wider market.

As it develops, the banana sale business faces challenges in terms of creativity, business location, and halal labeling. Creativity plays a role in product innovation, such as flavor variations and attractive packaging designs (Sitepu, 2019), but there are still business operators who use old and unhygienic packaging, thereby reducing consumer confidence. Strategic locations such as along the Medan–Banda Aceh road provide access advantages (Aji & Listyaningrum, 2021), although limited facilities such as parking and cleanliness can affect customer comfort. Halal labeling also increases confidence in product quality and safety (Rohim & Priyatno, 2021), but not all businesses have official certification. Based on a pre-survey of 30 businesses in Lhoknibong, the average daily income ranges from IDR 500,000 to IDR 1,000,000 depending on the type and quantity of products, but it is still volatile due to market demand and limited shelf life. Therefore, the study entitled "The Effect of Creativity, Business

Location, and Halal Label on the Income of Banana Sale Business Actors in East Aceh” aims to analyze the effect of these three factors on local business income.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Creativity

Creativity can be defined as the creation of new, useful ideas (Entrialgo & Iglesias, 2020). Creativity begins with a person's imagination, which allows individuals to transform ideas into innovative and valuable works. Unlike negative imagination, which is useless, positive imagination can encourage the emergence of new, useful and creative ideas. Tri Winda Saputri (2023) found that this type of creativity is an integral part of entrepreneurial skills essential for starting and growing a successful business. Wijaya (2023) defines creativity as the human ability to make new discoveries, which can be ideas or concrete works that are novel and different from what is generally known.

According to Gita Carlina (2022), the indicators used to measure creativity are as follows:

1. Critical thinking,
2. Optimistic,
3. Flexible,
4. Looking for solutions to problems, and
5. Likes to imagine.

Business Location

Location is the place where a business is conducted (Susanti et al., 2021). Selecting a strategic business location can increase competitiveness and increase the chances of business success in the market. Similarly, Aji and Listyaningrum (2021) state that a business location is an area where business actors carry out their duties, with ease of access as a consideration for achieving maximum revenue. Hidayat (2020) also argues that a strategic location is one that is easily accessible to consumers and frequently visited by people.

According to Abid Muhtarom (2022), the indicators used to assess business location are:

1. Location accessibility,
2. Smooth access to the location,
3. Proximity of location,
4. Safe and spacious atmosphere

Halal Label

A halal label is the inclusion of a word or statement on product packaging to indicate that the product is halal (Susilawati and Joharudin, 2023). This aligns with Islamic teachings, which emphasize the importance of choosing foods that are not only halal but also thayyib (good for consumption) (Rohim & Priyatno, 2021). According to Desmayonda and Trenggana (2019), halal labels serve not only as a marker of a product's halal status but also as an effective promotional tool.

Halal label indicators according to Hasniar et.al (2025) are:

1. Picture,
2. Writing
3. Combination of images and text, and
4. Stick to the packaging

Income

Revenue is defined as the result of a company's sales of goods or services during a specific period (Khaeria et al., 2023). Yuyun (2021) explains that revenue includes all receipts, both in the form of goods and cash, from other parties, as well as industrial output, which is valued based on the prevailing monetary value of assets at that time. Hafiz & Satrianto (2022) also add that revenue can be considered the profit a company earns from products sold.

According to Irfinanda (2022), income indicators consist of 3 indicators, namely:

1. Adequacy in financing needs,
2. Increased yield and
3. Experiencing development.

RESEARCH METHODS

The object of this research is the banana sale business actors with the research location being in Lhoknibong, Pante Bidari District, East Aceh Regency.. The population in this study was all banana sale businesses operating in Lhoknibong, Pante Bidari District, East Aceh Regency, a total of 35 businesses obtained from data from the village head of Pante Panah, Lhoknibong. The technique used in determining the number of samples was the saturated sampling method. Saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all members are used as samples. Another term for a saturated sample is a census. Because the population is quite small, namely 35 people, the entire population was sampled. Thus, the number of respondents studied was 35 people (Sugiyono 2015). The data collection technique used in this study was a questionnaire. This questionnaire is a list of statements made by the researcher and must be answered by the respondents. Questionnaires were distributed to the research respondents, the distribution of questionnaires was done manually by visiting the business owners directly to ensure the data obtained is more accurate and representative. The type of data used in this study is primary data, primary data obtained from the results of questionnaires filled out by business owners inLhoknibong, Pante Bidari District, East Aceh Regency.Data was measured using a Likert scale. Measurement of the analyzed data was carried out by providing indicators for each question asked using an interval scale, which has five assessment categories: strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

Validity testing is carried out to ensure that the research instrument used actually measures the variables that should be measured. To measure the validity of the data studied, it can be done by comparing the calculated r with the table r, for degree of freedom (df) = n-2 or 33, and a significance level of 0.05. The value of the r-table, as determined by the r-table, is 0.333. If the calculated r value > r table, then the test is valid, whereas if the calculated r value < r table, then the test is invalid. The validity test was carried out using the SPSS program with the following results:

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variable	No. Item	Calculated r Value	Table r Value	Description
Creativity (X1)	1	0.537	0.333	Valid
	2	0.766	0.333	Valid
	3	0.639	0.333	Valid
	4	0.533	0.333	Valid
	5	0.823	0.333	Valid
Business Location (X2)	1	0.773	0.333	Valid
	2	0.466	0.333	Valid
	3	0.583	0.333	Valid
	4	0.754	0.333	Valid
Halal Label (X3)	1	0.910	0.333	Valid
	2	0.964	0.333	Valid
	3	0.963	0.333	Valid
	4	0.976	0.333	Valid
Income (Y)	1	0.847	0.333	Valid
	2	0.872	0.333	Valid
	3	0.714	0.333	Valid

Based on the table above, the results of data processing show that all calculated r values > r table, namely 0.333 with a significance level (α) = 5% or 0.05. Thus, all statement items used in the questionnaire for creativity (X1), business location (X2), halal label (X3), and income (Y) are declared valid and suitable for use as measuring tools in this study.

Reliability Test

This reliability test was conducted using the Cronbach Alpha method. An instrument is considered reliable if the Cronbach Alpha coefficient value is > 0.60 (Sugiyono, 2016).

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha Calculated Value	Description
Creativity (X1)	0.650	Reliabel
Business Location (X2)	0.802	Reliabel
Halal Label (X3)	0.966	Reliabel
Income (Y)	0.730	Reliabel

Based on Table 2 above, it can be seen that all items on creativity (X1), business location (X2), halal label (X3), and income (Y) are considered reliable because according to the information for each variable, the Cronbach Alpha exceeds 0.60, so all items in this study are considered reliable and can be used to test the hypothesis.

Normality Test

The normality test aims to assess the extent to which the standardized residual data in a regression model is normally distributed. In this study, researchers used the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, where data is declared normally distributed if the significance value is greater than 0.05 (Ghozali, 2019).

Table 3. Normality Test Results One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov

		Unstandardized Residual
N		35
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.41675843
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.115
	Positive	.091
	Negative	-.115
Test Statistic		.115
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c		.200 ^d

Based on the table above, the Asymp.Sig significance value is 0.200, which is higher than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. The assumption or requirement for normality in the model has been met. The following results of the graph and histogram tests can be seen below:

Figure 1. Normality Probability Plot

Based on the image, the data is spread around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line, so it can be concluded that the data in the regression model of this study is normally distributed. Normality can also be seen through a histogram. If the histogram shows a bell-shaped shape, then the data can be concluded to be normally distributed.

Figure 2. Histogram

Based on the image, it shows that the data is bell-shaped, so it can be concluded that the data in this regression is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

This measurement aims to determine whether there is a high correlation between the independent variables in the regression model formed. The regression model is declared free of multicollinearity if the TOL value is > 0.10 and the VIF value is < 10.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	6.303	1.841		3.425	.002		
Total Variable Creativity (X1)	.284	.101	.493	2.820	.008	.720	1.389
Total Variable Business Location (X2)	.055	.083	.115	.664	.512	.731	1.368
Total Variable Halal Label (X3)	.002	.050	.005	.032	.974	.969	1.032

Based on the table, it can be seen that the three independent variables have a tolerance value greater than 0.1 and a VIF value less than 10. So it can be stated that the regression model in this study does not experience multicollinearity problems.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is a test carried out to determine whether in the regression model there is inequality in the variance of the residuals from one observation to another.

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the figure above, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in this study. This is based on the graph, where the points in the graph do not form a clear pattern and are scattered above and below the number 0 on the Y-axis.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	6.303	1.841		3.425	.002
Total Variable Creativity (X1)	.284	.101	.493	2.820	.008
Total Variable Business Location (X2)	.055	.083	.115	.664	.512
Total Variable Halal Label (X3)	.002	.050	.005	.032	.974

Based on the results of multiple linear regression using SPSS 27, the regression equation is:

$$Y = 6.303 + 0.284X_1 + 0.055X_2 + 0.002X_3 + e$$

From this equation it can be explained that:

1. The constant of 6.303 shows that if the variables Creativity (X₁), Business Location (X₂), and Halal Label (X₃) have a value of zero, then the value of Income (Y) is at 6.303.
2. The coefficient of X₁ (0.284) indicates that, assuming all other factors remain constant, a one unit increase in Creativity will result in a 0.284 increase in Income.
3. Assuming all other factors remain the same, the coefficient of X₂ (0.055) indicates that every one unit increase in Business Location will increase Revenue by 0.055.
4. The coefficient X₃ (0.002) indicates that, assuming other variables remain constant, every one unit increase in Halal Label will increase Revenue by 0.002.

Partial Significance Test (t-Test)

The test was conducted with a significance level of 5% and degrees of freedom (df) = n - k - 1 = 35 - 3 - 1 = 31, resulting in a t-table value of 2.039.

Table 6. Partial Significance Test (t-Test)

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	6.303	1.841		3.425	.002
Total Variable Creativity (X1)	.284	.101	.493	2.820	.008
Total Variable Business Location (X2)	.055	.083	.115	.664	.512
Total Variable Halal Label (X3)	.002	.050	.005	.032	.974

The results of the partial test (t-test) based on the table above show:

1. The creativity variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on income (t count 2.820 > t table 2.039; sig. 0.008 < 0.05), so H1 is accepted.
2. The business location variable (X2) does not have a significant effect on income (t count 0.664 < t table 2.039; sig. 0.512 > 0.05), so H2 is rejected.
3. The halal label variable (X3) also does not have a significant effect on income (t count 0.032 < t table 2.039; sig. 0.974 > 0.05), so H3 is rejected.

Coefficient of Determination (R²) Test

The coefficient of determination (R²) aims to determine how much an independent variable can explain its dependent variable. The results of the coefficient of determination test can be seen in the following table:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination (R²) Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.563*	.317	.251	1.484

Based on the table above, the coefficient of determination R² is 0.317, indicating that the income of banana chips businesses in East Aceh is influenced by creativity, business location, and halal labeling by 31.7%. The remaining 68.3% is influenced by factors not examined in this study.

Discussion

The Influence of Creativity on Business Actors' Income

The results of the hypothesis test show that creativity has a positive and significant effect on income ($t = 2.820 > 2.039$; $sig = 0.008 < 0.05$), so H1 is accepted. These results align with research by Cemosia et al. (2020), Hariyanto et al. (2023), and Harahap et al. (2021), but differ from those by Aisyah et al. (2024), Supit et al. (2022), and Arhasy et al. (2024), which found no significant effect.

The Influence of Business Location on Business Actors' Income

The results of the hypothesis test show that business location does not significantly affect income ($t = 0.664 < 2.039$; $sig = 0.512 > 0.05$), so H2 is rejected. This means that business location is not the main factor in increasing the income of banana sale entrepreneurs in East Aceh. This result is in line with research by Salim et al. (2024), Putri et al. (2023), and Andika et al. (2021), but differs from Astutik et al. (2024), Marfuah et al. (2019), and Zebua (2023) which state that location can significantly affect income.

The Impact of Halal Labels on Business Actors' Income

The results of the hypothesis test show that the halal label does not have a significant effect on income ($t = 0.032 < 2.039$; $sig = 0.974 > 0.05$), so H3 is rejected. This result is in line with the research of Rezi et al. (2023), Yuwono et al. (2023), and Handayani (2023), but differs from Hasniar et al. (2025), Mayangsari et al. (2022), and Safitri et al. (2024) which stated that the halal label has a significant effect on income.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that:

1. Creativity has a positive and significant effect on the income of banana sale businesses in Lhoknibong. The majority of respondents agree that the ability to create product variations, packaging innovations, and business idea development are the main factors in increasing income and business sustainability.
2. Business location does not have a significant effect on income. Although a strategic location facilitates consumer access, most business owners have been established for a long time and are known to customers, so location is no longer a dominant factor in increasing income.
3. Halal labeling also does not have a significant effect on income. Although important for consumer trust, statistically halal labeling has not had a real impact because the community already considers banana sale products to be culturally halal.

REFERENCES

- Agustinawati, A. (2024, January). Economic Productivity Of Female Entrepreneurs In The Culinary Tourism In Aceh. In Proceedings of Malikussaleh International Conference On Education Social Humanities And Innovation (Miceshi) (Vol. 1, pp. 0061-0061).
- Agustinawati, A., Bahri, H., Samsidar, S., & Yusuf, M. (2024). Bouquet Making as a Creative Business Opportunity for Teenagers in Blang Bayu Village, Syamtalira Bayu District, North Aceh Regency. *Journal of Economic and Social Service (JPES)*, 3(1), 43-46.

- Agustinawati, A., Suhani, C. I., & Yusuf, M. (2024). Training in Banana Debag Processing as an Entrepreneurial Opportunity for Young Women in Gampong Meunasah Ujong Kulam Matang Kuli. *Journal of Creative Service (JPeK)*, 3(2), 25-29.
- Agustinawati, S., Bahri, H., & Juliana, P. (2021). The Influence of Customer-Centric Strategy on Tourist Satisfaction. *International Journal of Economic Business, Accounting, Agriculture, Management, and Sharia Administration*, 1(2), 347-354.
- Agustinawati, A. (2016). Analysis of the Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in the Culinary Business Using the SERVQUAL Approach. *Visionary & Strategic Journal*, 5(2).
- Aji, AW, and Listyaningrum, SP (2021). The Influence of Business Capital, Business Location, and Information Technology on MSME Income in Bantul Regency. *JIAI (Indonesian Accounting Scientific Journal)*, 6(1).
- Arida, A., Mujiburrahmad, M., & Anwar, S. (2019). Analysis of Superior Food Crop Commodities in East Aceh Regency. *AGRIFO Journal*. Vol, 4(1).
- Arlena. WM (2023). Five Regions of Aceh: Main Pillars of Agriculture Driving the Local Economy. *Indonesian Journal of Agriculture and Agribusiness*.
- Asrarul Aini, TMN (2018). Profitability of Banana Chips Business in Lhok Nibong Village, Pante Bidari District, East Aceh Regency. *Agricultural Journal*, 2 (6):553.
- Carlina, G., & Ekowati, S. (2022). The Influence of Creativity and Innovation on Consumer Purchase Interest of O'Boss Meatballs in Bengkulu City. *Ekombis Review: Scientific Journal of Economics and Business*, 10(2), 599-608.
- Desmayonda, Ananda, and Arlin Ferlina. 2019. "The Influence of Halal Labels on Purchasing Decisions with Religiosity as an Intervening Variable at Mujigae Resto Bandung.
- Entrialgo, M., and Iglesias, V. (2020). Entrepreneurial intentions among university students: The moderating role of creativity. *Eur. Manag. Rev.* 17, 529–542. doi: 10.1111/emre.12386
- Ghozali, Imam. 2018. *Multivariate Analysis Application with IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- Hafiz, & Satrianto. (2022). The Effect of Capital and Production Costs on the Revenue of PT Minang Sukses Sejahtera. *JKEP: Journal of Economic and Development Studies*, Volume 4, Number 2, June 2022, Pages 37-44.
- Hafiz, & Satrianto. (2022). The Effect of Capital and Production Costs on the Revenue of PT Minang Sukses Sejahtera. *JKEP: Journal of Economic and Development Studies*, Volume 4, Number 2, June 2022, Pages 37-44.
- Hasniar, AR, & Jumriani. (2025). Mediation of Purchasing Decisions Based on Halal Labels on the Income of Food and Beverage MSMEs in Watampone. *Journal of Economics, Management, and Accounting*, Vol. 4, No. 2.
- Hidayat, T. (2020). Analysis of the Influence of Product, Price, Promotion, and Location on Purchasing Decisions. *Journal of Management Science*, 17(2), 109-119.
- Khaeria, AN, Luh Putu Tirta Murthi, N., Putra Triadji, T., & Yoan Nurotul Azizah, C. (2023). Income and Expenses. *Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal*, 2(2).
- Maulana, N., & Fitri, Y. (2023). Implementation of Corporations, Capacity and Financing of Creative Economy-Based MSMEs as Economic Drivers in Aceh. *Jurnal Cendikia Niaga (JCN)*, 7(2), 109-120.
- Muhtarom, A., Syairozi, MI, & Yonita, HL (2022). Analysis of Perception of Price, Location, Facilities, and Service Quality on Customer Loyalty Mediated in Purchasing Decisions (Case Study at SKCK MSME (Culinary Station Canditunggul Kalitengah) Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Method-Partial Least. *EKOMBIS REVIEW: Scientific Journal of Economics and Business*, 10(S1), 391-402.
- Rohim, AN, & Priyatno, PD (2021). Consumption Patterns in the Implementation of a Halal Lifestyle. *Maro: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business*, 4(2), 26–35.
- Sitepu. (2019). *Developing Student Writer Creativity*. Guepedia Publisher.
- Subhan, M., Sinurat, M., Lilinesia, L., & Simanjuntak, A. (2021). The culinary sector MSME survival strategy in an effort to restore populist economy based on the creative industry during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Management Research and Behavior Journal*, 1(1), 7-14.
- Susanti, D. (2021). The Influence of Product Quality on Consumer Interest in Purchasing Tupperware Products at the Griya Tika Utama Housing Complex in Pekanbaru. *Menara Ekonomi*, 3(5), 23–32.
- Susilawati, C., & Joharudin, A. (2023). Halal Labeling and Purchase Intention on Non-Food Halal Products.
- Tri Winda Saputri. (2023). Entrepreneurial Motivation and Creativity. *Journal of Creative Student Research (JCSR)*, Vol.1, No.2.

THE EFFECT OF CREATIVITY, BUSINESS LOCATION AND HALAL LABELS ON THE INCOME OF SALE BANANA BUSINESS ACTORS IN EAST ACEH

Rahmatillah et al

- Wijaya, WR, & Handoyo, SE (2023). The Influence of Social Media, Creativity, and Motivation on the Success of Culinary MSMEs in North Jakarta. *Journal of Managerial and Entrepreneurship*, 5(3), 797-804.
- Yuyun. (2021). Analysis of Working Capital and Financial Management on the Income of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) (Case Study of MSME Chicken Nobon Samarinda). *Borneo Studies and Research*, 2(2), 1261-1269.